

Radiolytic and photolytic preparation of metal nanoparticles[†]

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Mercurous ion, Hg_2^{2+} , is radiolytically reduced in an aqueous solution containing ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) as a ligand. Unlike, in the case of Ag_2^+ and Tl_2^+ ions no shift in the absorption band of Hg_2^+ is observed. On irradiation of different ratios of $\text{Hg}_2^{2+} : \text{Ag}^+$ ions in the presence of the ligand, formation of a mixed cluster is observed. It is concluded that the collective excitation of the electron gas in the mixed particles contributes to the optical absorption when the concentration of Ag^+ ion is less than that of Hg_2^{2+} ion. In the presence of 1 : 1 $\text{Hg}_2^{2+} : \text{Ag}^+$, the electron gas in the silver particles strongly contributes to the optical absorption spectrum. Electron microscopy reveals that particles of different sizes between 10–20 nm are present. Experiments with β -cyclodextrin show that the hydrophobic cavity of β -cyclodextrin can be utilized for stabilization of such metal clusters. Copper metal nanoparticles have been formed by irradiation with 253.7 nm light from a low pressure Hg-arc lamp in the presence of a protective agent such as carboxymethyl cellulose and gelatin. The nanoparticles have been characterized by their absorption maxima and transmission electron micrographs. The quantum yields of formation of the metal nanoparticles increase in the presence of the stabilizer as well as in the presence of a photosensitizer, benzophenone (BP).

Research on metal nanoparticles is greatly stimulated because of the unique properties of nanoscopic materials compared to the bulk metals. Synthesis of highly dispersed nanoparticles is challenging and therefore many efforts and experimental approaches have been initiated to prepare metal nanoparticles¹⁻¹⁶. This is very important because the studies on metal nanoparticles are evolving to find applications in biology and environment besides many other technological applications. For example, chemical species involving mercury are highly toxic contaminants of the environment, and their dissemination in aqueous medium is governed by sorption processes on biological, organic and inorganic particles¹⁷. Mercury is also a pollutant of considerable concern in aquatic ecosystems due to its strong tendency to bioaccumulate up the food chain and its demonstrated link to human health effects. Despite considerable work in recent years, the presence of mercury in the environment remains a serious problem, especially because of its high toxicity and its ionic mobility in soils and natural waters¹⁸. Several investigations have been devoted to better understanding of adsorption (and/or desorption) mechanisms and to find efficient scavengers for remediation purpose. Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), a strong chelating agent, is generally used in various applications, such as water softening, industrial cleaning, etc. Therefore, the extraction of metals from simple and complex solids by using complexing agents such as EDTA has been extensively reported¹⁹. The other complexing agents being explored for

metal ions/metals are crown ethers, cyclodextrins, etc.²⁰.

It has been demonstrated that preparations of metal nanoparticles using radiolytic and photolytic techniques are clean as no reductant is added from the outside⁴⁻¹¹. Fast techniques, encompassing lasers and electron beam, can be utilized for preparation as well as for the study of the mechanisms involved in the formation of metal nanoparticles. It is known that metal nanoparticles have different electrochemical potential as compared to that of the bulk metal. The change in the electrochemical properties of the metal ion can be studied using pulse radiolysis technique and one can be selective to carry out redox reactions. Hence, the variation in electrochemical potential of metal ions and their initial clusters can be studied by taking different concentration of metal ions in the solution. In the present article, we present part of the results obtained in our laboratory on the studies of metal nanoparticles using radiolytic and photochemical techniques.

Results and discussion

The absorption spectrum of the transient formed after 7 μs of irradiation by 50 ns electron pulses in N_2 -bubbled aqueous solution containing $0.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ Hg}_2^{2+}$ and 0.2 mol dm^{-3} propan-2-ol in unbuffered solution (pH 4.5) is shown in Fig. 1. The transient so obtained showed a broad absorption. It has been reported that at pH 2.3, H^\bullet reacts with Hg_2^{2+} to give Hg_2^+ which absorbs at 285 nm²¹⁻²³. Fig. 2 shows the decay traces obtained at different wavelengths.

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

Fig. 1. Transient absorption spectrum obtained following irradiation with 50 ns electron pulse of solutions containing 0.5×10^{-5} mol dm^{-3} Hg_2^{2+} , 0.2 mol dm^{-3} propan-2-ol at pH 4.5, ($[e_{\text{aq}}^-] = 4.5 \times 10^{-6}$ mol dm^{-3}).

Fig. 2. Kinetic traces of the transients obtained at various wavelengths on pulse irradiation. The solution and conditions are the same as in Fig. 1. Inset: decay of e_{aq}^- at 700 nm.

As can be seen from the traces, the transient absorption curve recorded at different wavelengths indicated the appearance of a species right after the pulse. Subsequently, the build-up and decay of a longer-lived intermediate can be observed over a longer time scale. It can be seen from the insert of Fig. 2 that e_{aq}^- decays much faster compared to the formation of the transient as observed at 285 nm (Fig. 1). Thus the transient belonging to the initial time-scale can be assigned to Hg_2^+ , which on reaction with Hg_2^{2+} leads to the formation of mercury clusters which absorb in the wavelength region 280–400 nm²⁴. It can be seen from Fig. 2 that formation rates are different at different wavelengths. This is due to the overlapping of the absorption bands due to various mercury clusters.

The absorption spectrum of the transient formed after 5 μs of irradiation by 50 ns electron pulses in N_2 -bubbled aqueous solution containing 0.5×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} Hg_2^{2+} , 5.0×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} EDTA and 0.2 mol dm^{-3} propan-2-ol at pH 10.2 is shown in Fig. 3. The transient so obtained showed a broad absorption. The hydrated electron can react with the ligand or metal ion in the complex. It is known that

Fig. 3. Transient absorption spectrum obtained following irradiation with 50 ns electron pulse of solutions containing 1.0×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} HgClO_4 , 5.0×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} EDTA, 0.2 mol dm^{-3} propan-2-ol at pH 10.2, ($[e_{\text{aq}}^-] = 4.5 \times 10^{-6}$ mol dm^{-3}). Inset: formation of transient at 280 nm.

e_{aq}^- reacts with EDTA²⁵ with a rate constant of $<10^5$ dm^3 mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ at pH 11. It is also known that Hg_2^{2+} forms a complex with EDTA which absorbs at 247 nm²⁶. Thus, the observed transient can be assigned to $\text{Hg}_2^+(\text{EDTA})^{4-}$. It can be seen from the insert of Fig. 3 that further growth of mercury clusters is much less pronounced as compared to the case where EDTA was not present in the solution (Fig. 2).

The electron affinity of Hg^+ is greater than that of Cd^+ due to the fact that 4*f*-shell in Hg shields the 6*s*-electron in a relatively poor manner. Hence the high ionization potential of Hg accounts somewhat for the noble character of Hg. Also, Hg_2^{2+} bond is stronger than Cd_2^{2+} bond. It is known that Hg_2^+ undergoes second order reaction²⁶. If for the formation of mercury particles, stabilization of Hg_2^+ is required, it appears that formation of Hg particles must be easy compared to that of Cd particles. In fact, it was observed that EDTA could stabilize Hg particles but turbidity appeared within one hour showing the agglomeration of particles, while it was not possible to stabilize Cd particles in the presence of EDTA.

As mentioned earlier, the variation in the redox potential of the metal ions and their clusters can be studied easily using the pulse radiolysis technique. Therefore, attempts have been made to prepare bimetallic clusters of Hg with Ag in the presence of EDTA. To understand the mechanism of electron transfer, pulse radiolysis experiments were carried out for solution containing $\text{Hg}_2^{2+}/\text{EDTA}$ at pH 10. No significant change was observed in the decay rate of $\text{Hg}_2^+(\text{EDTA})^{4-}$ in the presence of Ag^+ (up to 1.0×10^{-5} mol dm^{-3}). Higher Ag^+ concentration could not be used due to the direct electron transfer reaction of e_{aq}^- with Ag^+ that made it difficult to interpret the results because of overlapping signals. The bimetallic solution to be irradiated contains HgClO_4 and AgClO_4 in a 50 : 50 ratio in the presence of

excess EDTA. In an equimolar solution of precursors, complexed Hg and Ag atoms were generated quite readily. Then the association of these atoms may involve the same or different metal species. The absorption spectrum of the irradiated solution is shown in Fig. 4a. The colour of the solution was yellowish. It can be noted that the absorption maximum lies at 385 nm, which is slightly blue-shifted as compared to that of pure silver sol that showed absorption maximum under identical conditions at 400 nm. It can be seen from Fig. 4a that the properties of the alloyed cluster are strongly dominated by those of Ag. Therefore, it was important to extend the study to metal ion mixtures containing less concentration of Ag⁺. Two other systems

Fig. 4. Absorption spectrum of a mixed solution after irradiation with train of electron pulses (dose = 300 Gy) containing various ratios of Hg²⁺ : Ag⁺: (a) 1 : 1 (b) 2 : 1 (c) 20 : 1.

containing HgClO₄ : AgClO₄ in the ratio 2 : 1 and 20 : 1 were irradiated using electron pulses and the results are shown in Fig. 4, curves b and c, respectively. It can be seen that as the Ag⁺ concentration decreases, a significant blue-shift in the band absorbing at 380 nm is observed. The results are similar to that obtained in Hg²⁺ : Ag⁺ solution²⁷. We have used electron accelerator, producing high dose rate irradiation, so that both metal ions are reduced simultaneously. The probability of the formation of bimetallic cluster is more under such conditions²⁸. It appears that when mercury and silver ions are in the ratio 2 : 1 and 20 : 1, respectively, both the metal ions are reduced. However, the contribution to the absorption spectra was more of Hg as it resembles similar spectral characteristics in which only Hg solution was irradiated. The solution also showed slight opalescence. The shoulder observed at 285 nm was probably caused by the colloidal Hg drops and hence the expected 275 nm absorption maximum²⁹ became broader in the presence of silver. It is known that EDTA can stabilize silver clusters³⁰. However, from the above results it is clear that EDTA can also stabilize Hg clusters as well as bimetallic clusters of Hg and Ag. Transmission electron microscopy shows that Ag clusters of 10–20 nm were present in a solution containing Ag⁺ ion more than 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³. It

thus seems that when mercurous ion concentration is more, Hg⁰ and Ag⁰ both were produced in solution. Once Ag⁺ concentration reaches 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ or comparable to Hg₂²⁺ concentration in a solution, the absorption spectrum is governed mainly by Ag clusters. The solutions were stable for 1 day and after that black precipitate was observed.

Atomic Hg is in 6s² 6p⁰ configuration. As the particle grows in size, the atomic 6s and 6p levels broaden into continuous bands as compared to discrete bands. Optical absorption spectra of Hg nanoparticles varying in the size range of 3–30 nm show changes in the spectra from an atom-like to a plasmon-like absorption with increasing nuclearity^{31,32}. It is noteworthy to mention here that this shift occurs at *n* ~ 8 beyond which the plasmon frequency is independent of the particle size. As mentioned above, Hg atom is a closed shell species with a 6p lowest unoccupied orbital capable of overlapping with other metal atoms which might have facilitated the alloying process in the presence of the ligand.

Cyclodextrins exhibit cyclic structures and serve as host molecules towards many organic substances due to the presence hydrophobic cavity³³. It has also been suggested that cyclodextrins can avoid undesirable branching reactions. An attempt has been made to see whether cyclodextrin cavity can stabilize metal nanoparticles. As the clusters in the beginning are ionic in nature, the possibility of their stabilization is very low. In fact, no change in the formation and decay traces of Ag⁰ and Ag₂⁺ was observed on pulse irradiation of N₂-bubbled aqueous solutions of 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ AgClO₄, 10⁻¹ mol dm⁻³ propan-2-ol at pH 7, both in the absence and presence of 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ β-cyclodextrin. Silver ions were reduced by a train of electron pulses (dose = 240 Gy) with the intention that once bigger particles of silver would grow, they may show some hydrophobicity and hence may get stabilized in the cavity of β-cyclodextrin. On pulse irradiation of N₂-bubbled aqueous solution containing 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ AgClO₄, 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ β-cyclodextrin and 2 × 10⁻¹ mol dm⁻³ propan-2-ol, the colour of the solution turned yellow. The characteristic spectrum is shown in Fig. 5a. The colour of the sol turned pinkish within 10 min showing that the particles had aggregated. The absorption spectrum of the pinkish sol, as shown in Fig. 5b, corresponds exactly to the sol that was obtained just after pulse irradiation of AgClO₄ solution without β-cyclodextrin. This shows that β-cyclodextrin shows some tendency to stabilize silver particles. Though thiolated β-cyclodextrin are being used to stabilize metal particles³⁴, it appears that metal particles can be stabilized in β-cyclodextrin if the metal ions are complexed with ligands which are more hydrophobic in nature.

Fig. 5. Absorption spectrum of a solution after irradiation with train of electron pulses (dose = 240 Gy) containing $1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ Ag}^+$, $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \beta\text{-cyclodextrin}$ and $0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ propan-2-ol}$: (a) after 3 min of irradiation, (b) after 10 min of irradiation.

Preparation of metal nanoparticles using photo-chemical method :

It is known that to inhibit the aggregation processes of initial metal clusters, polymers and complexing agents serve as stabilizing agents⁵⁻⁷. Therefore, the photolysis of the aqueous CuSO_4 solution was done in the presence of gelatin or carboxymethylcellulose (CMC) as stabilizers, both in the presence and absence of photosensitizer benzophenone (BP).

Before studying the formation of nanoparticles by UV-irradiation using BP, it is vital to investigate how BP molecules react and how its concentration changes with UV-irradiation both in the presence and absence of metal salt solutions. It was observed that concentration of BP decreased at a slower rate in the presence of Cu-salt as compared to its absence in the solution. The amount of BP remaining in the solution was estimated spectrophotometrically by monitoring its absorption at 255 nm ($\epsilon = 1.4 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$), the maxima of its $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ absorption band^{35,36}. A quantitative analysis of the spectral changes leads to the conclusion that the photoreaction of BP proceeds at faster rate in the absence of Cu-salt solution because in its presence some intensity of light is also absorbed by Cu-salt solution. It was observed that the photochemical formation of Cu nanoparticles was accompanied by the photobleaching of BP. Fig. 6 shows the appearance of the surface plasmon absorption band due to Cu nanoparticles^{29,37-40} with increase in irradiation time on irradiation with 253.7 nm light for aqueous CuSO_4 solution with BP and gelatin in N_2 -bubbled solution. It can be seen from Fig. 6 that after 6 min of irradiation, no significant change was observed in the intensity of surface plasmon absorption band of Cu particles indicating complete reduction of Cu^{2+} to Cu metal.

The variation in the intensity of the surface plasmon absorption band of Cu nanoparticles with respect to irradiation time for stabilizers gelatin and carboxymethyl-cel-

Fig. 6. Change in the absorption spectra of N_2 -bubbled aqueous solution containing CuSO_4 ($2.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), BP ($2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and 0.5% (w/v) gelatin on UV photolysis. The number on spectra indicates the time of irradiation, path length = 1 cm.

lulose is shown in Fig. 7. It can be seen that the absorbance due to formation of Cu nanoparticles reaches a plateau value after 8 min of irradiation for both stabilizers.

Transmission electron micrograph images and corresponding diffraction pattern for copper nanoparticles are

Fig. 7. Change in the optical density due to copper particles in N_2 -bubbled solution containing CuSO_4 ($2.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) (a) in presence of $2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (BP) : N_2 -bubbled (\bullet) 0.5% (w/v) gelatin; (\blacksquare) 0.5% (w/v) CMC, (b) in absence of BP : (\blacktriangle) N_2 -bubbled solution containing CuSO_4 ($2.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and 0.5% (w/v) gelatin.

shown in Figs. 8 and 9 for stabilizers gelatin and CMC, respectively. Transmission electron micrographs show that the size of the particles was in the range of 10–15 nm for gelatin (Fig. 8) while for CMC it was 30–40 nm (Fig. 9). The particles were nearly spherical in nature. It appears that smaller particles of copper can be prepared using gelatin. This could be due to the strong interaction of Cu^{2+} ions with gelatin moieties⁴¹.

Fig. 8. TEM image and corresponding diffraction pattern of Cu nanoparticles prepared in N_2 -bubbled aqueous solution containing 0.5% (w/v) gelatin, $2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ BP and $2.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ $CuSO_4$.

Fig. 9. TEM image of Cu nanoparticles prepared in N_2 -bubbled aqueous solution containing 0.5% (w/v) CMC, $2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ BP and $2.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ $CuSO_4$.

Formation of Cu nanoparticles in the presence of various stabilizers was also studied by absorption spectroscopy without adding benzophenone. Only in the case of gelatin, a distinct absorption peak of Cu nanoparticles near 560 nm developed (Fig. 7) while no spectral changes were observed for aqueous solutions containing $CuSO_4$ and CMC. The very light pink colour of Cu sol was observed in the solution containing $CuSO_4$ and gelatin. This colour did not change much with irradiation time (Fig. 7). As no sign of Cu sol formation was observed when CMC/ Cu^{2+} solutions were irradiated it appears that neither the excited Cu^{2+} nor CMC could induce the photo-oxidation of water. The formation of Cu sol in the solution containing gelatin shows that the excited gelatin might have contributed to its formation as gelatin contains amide bonds in addition to various amino acids. It has been shown earlier that Cu^{2+} forms a complex with gelatin⁴¹. Thus it appears that the excitation of amide or amino acid moieties in gelatin leads to the reduction of Cu^{2+} to metallic Cu. The reduction from Cu^{2+} to the metal, however, did not occur on leaving aqueous $CuSO_4$ solution containing gelatin under dark conditions. The above results demonstrate the role played by the stabilizer in stabilizing the metal nanoparticles.

To demonstrate the mechanism of formation of copper nanoparticles in the presence of benzophenone, laser flash photolysis experiments were carried out at $20 \pm 1^\circ$. Samples were excited with the fourth harmonic output pulses (266 nm, 2 mJ) of 35 ps duration from an active passive mode-locked Nd : YAG laser (Continuum model 501C-10) and the absorption of transients was measured using a Xe-arc lamp. On excitation of an aqueous solution containing $2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ benzophenone, the transient absorption of

the excited triplet state was measured. The triplet absorption spectrum for BP had a maximum at 525 nm, and it extended above 600 nm. The observed spectrum was similar to that reported recently for triplet BP in water⁴². The kinetics for the decay of triplet benzophenone was found to be first-order with a lifetime of more than 7 μ s. On addition of gelatin or CMC (0.1%) the triplet benzophenone, ³BP*, was found to react with them to produce the spectral characteristics of the benzophenone ketyl-radical with absorbance in the wavelength range of 470–600 nm. This behavior demonstrates that ³BP* readily abstracts hydrogen atoms from gelatin or CMC. Thus development of Cu surface plasmon absorption band in aqueous solution of CuSO₄ containing BP can be explained in terms of the formation of triplet BP*. In solutions containing BP, 253.7 nm light is absorbed by BP and excited BP leads to the following reactions^{35,36} :

where RH denotes the stabilizer molecule and R* an alkyl radical formed from the stabilizer, respectively. It can be assumed that BP ketyl radical (C₆H₅)₂C*(OH) (BPK) reduces copper ions and copper ion clusters. Subsequent agglomeration processes of Cu atoms and clusters produced Cu nanoparticles^{39,40}. Thus it can be inferred that photochemical methods have equal potential to prepare small metal nanoparticles both by direct and indirect processes.

Experimental

Radiolytic reduction : The pulse radiolysis setup consists of an electron linear accelerator (Forward Industries, England) capable of giving single pulses of 50 or 500 ns or 2 μ s of 7 MeV electrons. The pulse irradiates the sample contained in a 1 cm \times 1 cm suprasil quartz cuvette kept at a distance of approximately 12 cm from the electron beam window, where the beam diameter was approximately 1 cm. The transient changes in the absorbance of the solution caused by the electron pulse were monitored with the help of a collimated light beam from a 450 W xenon arc lamp. The output from the PMT was fed through a DC offset circuit to the Y input of a L & T storage scope which can transfer 400 megasamples/s on each input channel at 250 ns/div time base range with sensitivity of 5 mV/div and having a bandwidth of 100 MHz. Further details of the LINAC can be seen elsewhere⁴³. An aerated 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ KSCN solution was used for dosimetry and (SCN)₂⁻

radical was monitored at 475 nm. The absorbed dose per pulse was calculated⁴⁴ assuming $G\varepsilon = 23889 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ per 100 eV, where G is the radiation chemical yield expressed as the number of molecules formed or destroyed per 100 eV of energy absorbed and ε the molar absorptivity. The dose employed in the present study, unless otherwise stated, was typically 16 Gy per pulse. However, a lower dose of about 9 Gy per pulse was used for the determination of formation rate constants and molar absorptivity.

One-electron reduction :

On irradiation of H₂O, the following primary radicals are produced^{25,45} :

To study the reaction of e_{aq}^- with mercurous complexes of EDTA, propan-2-ol in a N₂-bubbled solution was used as the scavenger for H*/OH* radicals according to reaction (5), H*/OH* + (CH₃)₂CHOH \rightarrow H₂/H₂O + (CH₃)₂C*OH (5)

Concentration of the hydrated electrons and (CH₃)₂C*OH radicals which is formed during the pulse are $G(e_{aq}^-)$ and $G(H^*) + G(OH^*)$, respectively. The $G(e_{aq}^-)$, $G(H^*)$ and $G(OH^*)$ values were taken as 0.28, 0.062 and 0.28 μ mol J⁻¹ from the literature^{25,45} [$G(e_{aq}^-) = 2.7 \text{ mol}/100 \text{ eV} = 2.8 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol J}^{-1}$, $G(H^*) = 0.6 \text{ mol}/100 \text{ eV} = 0.62 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol J}^{-1}$, $G(OH^*) = 2.8 \text{ mol}/100 \text{ eV} = 2.8 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol J}^{-1}$].

The mercurous ion concentration was varied from 0.5 \times 10⁻⁴ to 2.0 \times 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ to determine the rate of reaction. Correspondingly, the concentration of the ligand was increased to keep the initial ratio of [Ligand]/[Hg⁺] constant and for complete complexation⁴⁶ of Hg⁺.

Photolytic reduction : Typically, de-aerated aqueous solution of metal salt (2.5 \times 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³) containing gelatin (0.5%, w/v) or CMC (0.5%, w/v) and benzophenone (BP) (2.0 \times 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³) was placed in a rectangular quartz cuvette (1 cm \times 1 cm \times 5 cm). 200 W Hg-lamps (Rayonet Photochemical Reactor) were used as the light source for 253.7 nm UV-light irradiation at an ambient temperature. The cell was placed in the reactor and 4–4.5 ml solution was put in it for photolysis. The incident photon number of 253.7 nm light (determined by a tris(oxalato) ferrate (111) actinometer⁴⁷ was 5.035 \times 10¹⁵ cm² s⁻¹).

Characterization : Samples for transmission electron microscopy (TEM) were prepared by putting a drop of the colloidal solution on a copper grid coated with a thin amorphous carbon film. Samples were dried and kept under vacuum in a desiccator before putting them in a specimen holder. The TEM characterization was carried out using a JEOL JEM-2000FX electron microscope. Particle sizes were

measured from the TEM micrographs. The particle size is defined as the average of the largest and shortest diameters of the particles. Absorption was measured on a Hitachi 330-A spectrophotometer. The spectra were recorded at room temperature using 1 cm quartz cuvette.

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References

- G. A. Ozin, *Adv. Mater.*, 1992, **4**, 612.
- D. S. Wang, M. Kerker and H. Chew, *Appl. Opt.*, 1990, **19**, 2135.
- L. Genzel and T. P. Martin, *Surf. Sci.*, 1973, **34**, 33.
- B. G. Ershov and A. Henglein, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1993, **97**, 3434.
- A. Henglein, P. Mulvaney, A. Holtzworth, T. Sosebee and A. Fojtik, *Ber. Bunsenges. Phys. Chem.*, 1992, **96**, 754.
- M. Gutierrez and A. Henglein, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1993, **97**, 11368.
- P. Mulvaney, T. Linnert and A. Henglein, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1991, **95**, 7843.
- Y. Yonezawa, T. Sato, M. Ohno and H. Hada, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1987, 1559.
- Y. Yonezawa, T. Sato and S. Kuroda, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1991, 1905.
- T. Sato, N. Maeda, H. Ohkoshi and Y. Yonezawa, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1994, **67**, 3165.
- T. Itakura, K. Torigoe and K. Esumi, *Langmuir*, 1995, **11**, 4129.
- R. B. Bright, M. D. Musick and M. J. Natan, *Langmuir*, 1998, **14**, 5695.
- N. Toshima, T. Yonezawa and K. Kushihashi, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1993, 2537.
- L. M. Liz-Marzan and I. Lado-Tourino, *Langmuir*, 1996, **12**, 3585.
- S. Kapoor, *Langmuir*, 1998, **14**, 1021.
- C. Petit, P. Lixon and M. P. Pileni, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1993, **97**, 12974.
- J. Westall in "Aquatic Surface Chemistry : Chemical Processes at the Particle-Water Interface", ed. W. Stumm, Wiley, New York, 1987.
- N. S. Bloom, G. A. Gill, S. Cappellino, C. Dobbs, L. McShea, C. Driscoll, R. Mason and J. Rudd, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 1999, **33**, 7.
- A. Barona and F. Romero, *Environ. Technol.*, 1996, **17**, 63.
- A. Bartsch, I. Goldber, D. A. Laidler, C. L. Liotta, J. F. Stoddart, J. L. Toner, F. Vogtle and E. Weber in "Crown Ethers and Analogs", eds. S. Patai and Z. Rappoport, New York, 1989.
- S. Fujita, H. Horii, T. Mori and S. Taniguchi, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1976, **49**, 1250.
- M. Faraggi and A. Amozig, *Int. J. Radiat. Phys. Chem.*, 1972, **4**, 353.
- A. K. Pikaev and G. K. Sibirskaya, *Radiochem Radioanal. Lett.*, 1979, **38**, 39.
- N. L. Sukhov and B. G. Ershov, *Bull. Russ. Acad. Sci., Divn. Chem. Sci.*, 1992, **41**, 1.
- G. V. Buxton, C. L. Greenstock, W. P. Helman and A. B. Ross, *J. Phys. Chem Ref. Data*, 1988, **17**, 513.
- S. Fujita, H. Horii and S. Tangiguchi, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1973, **77**, 2868.
- L. Katsikas, M. Gutierrez and A. Henglein, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1996, **100**, 11203.
- M. Treguer, C. de Cointet, H. Remita, J. Khatouri, M. Mostafavi, J. Amblard, J. Belloni and R. de Keyzer, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1998, **102**, 4310.
- J. A. Creighton and D. G. Eadon, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1991, 3881.
- S. Remita, M. Mostafavi and M. -O. Delcourt, *New. J. Chem.*, 1994, **18**, 581.
- H. Haberland, B. von Issendorf, Y. Yufeng, J. Kolar and G. Z. Thanner, *Phys. D At Mol. Clusters*, 1993, **26**, 8.
- C. N. R. Rao, G. U. Kulkarni, P. J. Thomas and P. P. Edwards, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2000, **29**, 27.
- V. Ramamurthy and D. F. Eaton, *Acc. Chem Res.*, 1988, **21**, 300.
- Y. Maeda, T. Fukuda, H. Yamamoto and H. Kitano, *Langmuir*, 1997, **13**, 4187.
- Y. Sakaguchi, S. Nagakura and H. Hayashi, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1982, **86**, 3177.
- Y. Sakaguchi, H. Hayashi and S. Nagakura, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1980, **72**, 420.
- G. Mie, *Ann. Phys.*, 1908, **25**, 377.
- A. Henglein, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1993, **97**, 5457.
- J. Khatouri, M. Mostafavi, J. Amblard and J. Belloni, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1992, **191**, 135.
- A. Henglein, M. Gutierrez, E. Janata and B. G. Ershov, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1992, **96**, 4598.
- S. Kapoor, M. Kumar and C. Gopinathan, *Radiat. Phys Chem.*, 1997, **50**, 465.
- O. Rinco, M. H. Kleinman and C. Bohne, *Langmuir*, 2001, **17**, 5781.
- T. Mukherjee in "Atomic, Molecular and Cluster Physics", ed. S. Ahmed, Narosa, New Delhi, 1997.
- G. V. Buxton and C. R. Stuart, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1995, 279.
- J. W. T. Spinks and R. J. Wood, "Introduction to Radiation Chemistry", Wiley, New York, 1990.
- A. E. Martell and R. M. Smith, "Critical Stability Constants", Plenum Press, New York, 1982.
- S. L. Murov, I. Carmichael and G. L. Hug, "Handbook of Photochemistry", 2nd. ed., Marcel Dekker, New York, 1993.

